

George J. Brooke and Charlotte Hempel (eds), *T&T Clark Companion to the Dead Sea Scrolls*. Bloomsbury T&T Clark, London, 2019. xiv, 657 pp. £130.00. ISBN 978 0 56735 205 7.

This volume brings together 73 contributors from across Europe, Israel and North America – all experts in the field of Qumran studies. The resulting 75 articles represent the finest and most comprehensive single volume on the subject to date. The *Companion to the Dead Sea Scrolls* is remarkable for its breadth and substantial treatment of the history and current state of scholarship in Qumran studies, as well as over thirty key texts and documents within the Dead Sea Scrolls corpus.

The aim of the editors was to provide a basic introduction to the Scrolls and their wider contexts, including their archaeological contexts. Significantly, there is a notable concern to address wider contemporary research issues and methodologies, demonstrating the breadth and depth of current academic engagement within the larger landscape of Qumran scholarship. Editorial intervention is limited to maintaining accessibility and ease of comprehension, and each contributor's unique style and approach is evident. The articles include helpful cross references to others within the volume, and each is accompanied by a substantial bibliography of the subject for further exploration.

The volume consists of six major sections. The first aptly begins with an exploration of the background of the Scrolls, and includes an overview of the manuscript collections and studies on their discovery, acquisition, publication and popular reception.

Hans Debel's contribution on the discoveries brings together many differing historical threads into an account which is both engaging and judicious. Dennis Mizzi's entry on the archaeology of Qumran is comprehensive, authoritative and up to date.

The second section seeks to place the Scrolls in wider sociological, geographical, ideological and textual contexts. Particularly insightful are Henryk Drawnel's contribution on the connection between Qumran and the wider ancient Near East (dealing specifically with Babylonian celestial knowledge and astronomy), George Brooke's examination of the Scrolls in light of early Judaism, and Albert Hogterp's chapter on early Christianity. Entries also address the Scrolls in light of Hellenistic Jewish literature, particularly Philo (Joan Taylor's contribution here is noteworthy), Josephus, and Hellenistic non-Jewish literature connected with associations and philosopher communities, Zoroastrianism and Hellenistic philosophy.

The third section showcases fresh insights derived from new methodological inquiries regarding the Scrolls. These new or renewed areas of study include material culture, manuscript reconstruction, philological and text-critical treatments, historiography and social-scientific approaches. Three notable contributions begin the section: Ingo Kottsieper

examines manuscript physicality and material culture as well as key scientific technologies, and Annette Steudel considers the reconstruction of manuscripts. The entry on historiography by the late Philip Davies demonstrates his trademark meticulousness on the subject. Matters of social sciences round out the section with contributions on sectarianism, sociolinguistics and identity theory. Maxine Grossman's exploration of the intersection of gender and sexuality studies and the Scrolls is superb, opening the door to new and significant questions in the field.

Attention turns to key texts within the Qumran corpus in the fourth section. Arranged alphabetically, the 32 entries cover not only major texts (such as the Damascus Document, Genesis Apocryphon, *Hodayot*, *Milḥamah*, *Serekh ha-Yahad*, Songs of the Sabbath Sacrifice, and the Temple Scroll) with excellence, but additionally cover individual compositions and constellations of texts which have been the focus of recent scholarship, such as *Miqṣat Ma'aseh ha-Torah*. Each entry offers an overview of the text(s), with attention to textual development, thematic elements, and the work's importance within the Qumran community or wider Second Temple contexts. The bibliographical information in this section is robust and offers the reader an excellent collection of principal scholarly works with other pertinent literature.

Part Five consists of studies addressing the types of literature found in the Scrolls. Molly Zahn's contribution on parabiblical texts and

rewritten Scripture in the Scrolls is worthy of attention as she thoughtfully re-evaluates the boundaries and limitations associated with such textual phenomena. Equally important are the entries on *halakhah* (Vered Noam), rule texts (Charlotte Hempel), liturgical texts (Daniel Falk), calendrical texts (Helen Jacobus) and wisdom (Matthew Goff). Each of the entries in this section demonstrates a judicious presentation of the literary contours of these groupings and a keen awareness of the limitation of genre analysis in exploring ancient texts.

The last section of the volume addresses various facets of communal life and ideology, including patriarchal and Aramaic traditions, revelation at Qumran, divine and demonic beings, Temple ideology, eschatology and messianism, and war and violence at Qumran. Cecilia Wassen's contributions on purity and holiness and on the community's daily life are impressive in scope and depth, as is Alison Schofield's contribution on the nature of the *Yahad*, which persuasively argues for a vision of the *Yahad* that encompasses various community expressions. Equally insightful is the chapter by Eibert Tigchelaar, who locates Qumran scribal culture within the larger landscape of scribal practice in the Second Temple period.

The volume concludes with a helpful collection of appendices, including a timeline of key events from 350 BCE to 150 CE, principal printed editions, electronic resources, major reference works, translations and introductory works. Additionally, the volume contains extensive indices of

ancient sources, modern authors and subjects.

In sum, the *Companion to the Dead Sea Scrolls* is an indispensable resource

for library collections and any individual scholar whose work touches on the texts discovered in the Judean desert.

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Mira Beth Wasserman, *Jews, Gentiles, and Other Animals: The Talmud after the Humanities*. University of Pennsylvania Press, Philadelphia PA, 2017. x, 314 pp. \$65.00. ISBN 978 0 81224 920 0.

Described on the jacket cover as ‘arguably the Talmud’s most scandalous tractate’, tractate *Avodah Zarah (AZ)*, with its focus on relations with non-Jews, has long been recognized as a text of great socio-cultural significance. In recent years it has been treated in several important books and shorter studies (e.g. C. Hayes, *Between the Babylonian and Palestinian Talmuds*, Oxford University Press, Oxford, 1997; A. Gray, *A Talmud in Exile: The Influence of Yerushalmi Avodah Zarah on the Formation of Bavli Avodah Zarah*, Brown Judaic Studies, Providence RI, 2005). This most recent work, entirely dedicated to *AZ*, is quite different; it does not engage with the Yerushalmi, but only with the Bavli, and applies to it an impressive range of novel, theoretical perspectives. Whether or not this tractate deserves the title of ‘most scandalous’ – I would consider *Sanhedrin* ch. 7 equally shocking and scandalous – it certainly has much to reveal about early rabbinic attitudes to what the author wittingly calls ‘Jews, Gentiles, and other animals’.

The book follows broadly the structure of the tractate and presents itself as a kind of modern, cutting-

edge philosophical commentary on it. The chapter division does not consistently match that of the tractate, but rather follows a set of leading themes. Chapter 1, largely on *AZ* ch. 1, introduces the reader to literary theorist Mikhail Bakhtin (following already the example of Daniel Boyarin) and to a recent philosophical movement known as ‘new materialisms’. The latter becomes a hermeneutical paradigm through the rest of the book, in its interpretation of Talmudic attitudes to Gentiles, animals and objects that are prohibited, in most cases, under the Halakhic category of ‘*avodah zarah*’. Thus Chapter 2, on a large part of *AZ* ch. 2, considers the Talmud’s association of humans, primarily Gentiles, with animals, and the sometimes fuzzy and compromised boundaries between animals and humans, Gentile as well as Jew. The discussion is largely informed by another emerging academic field known as ‘animal studies’, itself an offshoot of a theoretical framework that is styled more generally ‘post-humanism’. I consider this the most interesting chapter of the book. Chapter 3, on non-Jewish wine (a theme that occupies part of *AZ* ch. 2,